

**WITCHCRAFT AS A SYSTEM OF SOCIAL ORDER IN ACHEBE'S
*THINGS FALL APART***

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Abstract

Colonialism was system of oppression which postulated superiority over marginal cultures. Colonialism realigned multiple aspects of African social existence through its transcendental agency shored up with Western military and economic might. The first casualty of such colonialist classification is the belief system of the traditional African people and their religion, a representation of their indigenous gods that was redefined through the agency of language. Witchcraft is negatively reappropriated by the colonialist having the agency of power and language in an attempt to reduce African religious practices as a narrow reality of evil and harm without the possibility of such religious social practices having varied interpretation beyond this restricted imposition of meaning. Through the application of postcolonial theory, this paper observes that Witchcraft performs the function of social order in *Things Fall Apart*. This concept of social order is multidimensional and could be interrogated from such concepts as: political, economic, socio-religious structures of the indigenous African society within the world of the novel. It accounts for various meanings of witchcraft within the Igbo traditional society. This paper applies the concept of Ashcroft's postcolonial theory and submits that; the dawn of colonialism disrupted traditional belief that has guided the African society as seen in Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*.

Keywords: Witchcraft, Social Order, Politics, Classification, Colonialism

La sorcellerie comme moyen du règlement social dans *Le monde s'effondre* d'Achebe

Résumé

Le colonialisme était un système d'oppression qui postulait la supériorité contre les cultures marginalisées. Le colonialisme reliait de multiples aspects de l'existence sociale africaine grâce à son agence transcendantale étayée par la puissance militaire et économique occidentale. La première victime d'une telle classification colonialiste est le système traditionnel de croyance du peuple africain et sa religion, la représentation de leurs dieux indigènes qui a été redéfinie par l'action menée dans le domaine linguistique. La sorcellerie est représentée négativement par les colons ayant le pouvoir et le langage, dans une tentative de réduire les pratiques religieuses africaines comme des réalités maladroites qui ne contenaient que du mal sans la possibilité que ces pratiques sociales religieuses aient une interprétation variée au-delà de cette imposition restreinte du sens. Grâce à l'application de la théorie postcoloniale, cet article observe que la sorcellerie remplit la fonction du règlement social dans *Le monde s'effondre*. Ce concept de règlement social est multidimensionnel et pourrait être interrogé à partir de concepts tels que: les structures politiques, économiques, socioreligieuses de la société africaine indigène dans le monde du roman. Il explique des diverses significations de la sorcellerie au sein de la société traditionnelle Igbo. L'article applique le concept de la théorie postcoloniale d'Ashcroft et postule que l'arrivée du colonialisme a détruit les croyances traditionnelles qui guidaient la société africaine, comme il est le cas présenté dans *Le monde s'effondre* d'Achebe.

Mots clés: Sorcellerie, règlement social, politique, classification, colonialisme

INTRODUCTION

Western scholars and popular imagination have constructed African witchcraft within the premise of negativity in their attempt to extend the binary argument of Western metaphysics and the narrow ambiguous line of imperialist delineation of good and evil. Some Western scholars in conditioning African imagination and socio-religious practices often add the prefix of evil after the definition of witchcraft practices in Africa. Thus, most of them define witchcraft as the use of magical or supernatural powers and then they add as an afterthought "for evil end", see Adam Ashforth, Boris Gershman, Lawrence Foana'ota, IWC Van Wyk., Matsobane J. Manaia, Bernard Gechiko Nyabwari et al, in their attempt to define witchcraft. Friday Mufuzi accounting for this negative portrayal notes; "Studies on witchcraft in colonial Africa in general... have focused on explaining the phenomenon in terms of the primitiveness of the practice and its practitioners. Most probably, this was done in order to justify colonialism in the area" (50). At the failure of western psychology, which is reflected in their scholarship and literary outputs, African creative literature through re-imagining the past,

properly captures the practice of witchcraft within the traditional preliterate society. Literature is a product of the society in the sense that the creative artist is conditioned by the norms and belief systems prevalent in his time. This is implicated in the artist's portrayal of reality in turn influenced by a certain notion of national consciousness.

Witchcraft, as a traditional spiritual craft, aids the art of governance and social relations within the Igbo society as depicted in the world of the novel, a notional representation of the material world in which the writer is a product of and assert a certain form of difference from the imperialist centre. Rebecca L. Stein and Philip L. Stein through functional portrayal of what is practised in Umuofia to a new colonial definition of few negative feelings, observe that "...functional' approaches are reductionist, reducing religion to a few feelings and behaviours that are not in themselves religious" (51). This also highlights the concept of essentialism. "Essentialism is the concept that things give a set pattern which make them what they are" (1). An essentialist definition of religion looks at what is the essential nature of religion. Essentialism emphasizes the fact that religion is the domain of the extraordinary- things beyond the common place and the natural. Philip L. Stein notes: "...a religion is a system of beliefs and behaviours that deals with the relationship between humans and sacred supernatural" (52). Witchcraft fits into such conceptualization. Witchcraft is a form of social order in Umuofia and it is the illustration of the hierarchical structures and ranks within the society and to some extent it is also a code of conduct that determines what is good or bad in the traditional Igbo society. Arinze Agbanusi argues that witchcraft is a concept of power defining it as "the use of magic powers" (117). Although all "religious powers" both in Christianity and African traditional religion appear to be extra-ordinary, the ones associated with activities of the imperialist religion are referred to as divine while those of African religion are referred to as evil and this is an illustration of the power of classification. Northrop Frye captures the structure of social order thus: divine world which is made of society of gods and one God, human world which is society of men which is one man, animal world which is sheepfold etc. (141). What this demonstrates is a constant interaction within the various worlds Frye highlighted. In a sense, these supernatural powers become communicative links for various forces that find meaning within their ambit of human cum metaphysical sphere. Friday Mufuzi's definition of witchcraft is implicated in the suggestion that: "...witchcraft is a theory of power and authority and practitioners believe that it possesses energies that could protect them against any kind of harm from their perceived enemies, and that it had the power to protect whatever wealth had been accumulated from destruction by supposed enemies who in general were either their...kin or close friends" (1). Witchcraft is a political religious system of

protection which results from the relationship and interaction between man and spirits and that innate desire to seek for something greater than man himself. This constitutes a form of social order that protects man from his immediate society and in the supreme natural world from all forces of the unknown that might portend evil. Tonia Umoren corroborated the foregoing in her definition of social order as:

...a patterned way of behaviour among people in a community. It is an order based on the collective consciousness of people. Consequently, the regularities and similarities in behaviour among a group transcend the action of the individual. Social order thus has to do with the role-play of individual members of the society in their interaction with the accustomed social restraints (1).

What Umoren did not highlight is the cyclical nature of the interaction of the world of the living and the dead as a singular presentation of dualism within the traditional Umuofia society. This pattern of behaviour is seen in the world of the supernatural that is closely linked to the material world of the living. Chinua Achebe in *Things Fall Apart* affirms this concept of the intertwining existence of the world of the living and the dead when he observes that:

Land of the living was not far removed from the domain of the ancestors. There was coming and going between them, especially at the festivals and also when an old man died, because an old man was very close to the ancestors. A man's life from birth to death was a series of transition rites which brought him nearer and nearer to his ancestors (97).

This interaction is that which occurs between mortals and the spirit. The medium of this interaction is spiritual of which witchcraft is a functional indication of a form of religious, political and social practice in Umuofia before the imposition of the imperialist methods of classification. Nyabwani et al note that

traditional power can be used to protect homes, families, fields, cattle, and other properties... Some people spend a great deal of wealth and effort to obtain magical protection and property. Among those who tap these magical powers for good or provide this protective gear are medicine men, diviners and rainmakers” (10).

Traditional system of power was deployed for protection.

Postcolonial criticism is concerned with the narratives emanating from the

Empire as a result of the collapse of colonialism. This theory accounts for how the Empire appropriating the continuum of the English language fashioned it within the traditional ideological stead of cultural practice that is alien to the English language and the colonial experience. The postcolonial models which emphasize national model or regional model of criticism to be applied in the analysis of the literatures that are produced by the Empire at the end of colonialism. This becomes handy in our alternate narratives against the demonization of witchcraft which is as a result of the ignorance of the European models of classification in its attempt to understand indigenous religious practices which it failed to properly account for. Bill Ashcroft et al observe that, "Post-colonial literatures developed through several stages which can be seen to correspond to stages both of national or regional consciousness and of the project of asserting difference from the imperial centre" (4). The portrayal of difference and a form of religious national consciousness is illustrated in the Umuofia religious system which is at variance from the imperialist Christianity highlighted in *Things Fall Apart*. Achebe's depiction of Umuofia's indigenous religious practice and appropriation of Igbo syntax for his narrative, is a stylistic means through which he weaponizes the language of the centre. Through this creative ingenuity, Achebe deploys the invasive language to his service thus enabling it to bear the linguistic weight of his own colonial experience. Ashcroft et-al observe that,

Language becomes the medium through which a hierarchical structure of power is perpetuated, and the medium through which conceptions of 'truth', 'order', and 'reality' become established. Such power is rejected in the emergence of an effective post-colonial voice. For this reason, the discussion of post-colonial writing which follows is largely a discussion of the process by which the language, with its power, and the writing, with its signification of authority, has been wrested from the dominant European culture (8).

Achebe through language establishes the religious, economic and political systems of Umuofia consistently different from the narrative of the imperialist centre. He portrays a worldview where the gods and humans share a form of consistent fluid space which one or the other makes a transition to the other in a continuous communing with the spirits and human.

WITCHCRAFT AND IMPERIALIST CLASSIFICATION

The power of classification yielded by the colonialist institution and practice was a total one that classified most African protects as evil. M. G Mokgobi corroborated the foregoing thus:

The colonial authorities and subsequently the apartheid government imposed a Western Worldview on the people of...Africa without an attempt to determine the validity of the worldview on issues such as traditional African healing and traditional African religion/spirituality, which are in most cases mutually interwoven (1).

Witchcraft, which is negatively classified as an afterthought, receives a prefix toward the end of its definition as a reflection of Western power of classification. The definition of witchcraft by some scholars such as Boris Gershman, Lawrence Foana'ota, IWC Van Wyk,, Matsobane J Manaia, Bernard Gechiko Nyabwari et al perpetuating western psychology sees witchcraft as a primary source of evil and badness in African society thereby conditions witchcraft in a negative light in the global and African society. However, Gbule J. Ndid and Odili Jones U. seem to have a proper conceptualization of witchcraft thus; "There are two kinds of witches. They are the black witch which is evil and the white witch which is harmless" (102). They provide proper classification of witchcraft which is premised on white and black, one which is evil and the other which is harmless, while most scholars have single imagining of witchcraft as a craft of evil without a possibility of being good. Daniel A. Offiong is of the same view that witches have two types far from the singularity of evil that Western scholarship and Christianity motivated scholars have imposed on such cultural practice. The "white" aspect of witchcraft is used for the service of the community (113). M.S Jayeola-Ompyeni et-al emphasizing the role of witchcraft in traditional society notes;

Witchcraft is the supernatural interface in the natural community lifestyle and behaviour. It is a universal phenomenon which has a strong root in community beliefs. Before civilization and technology, almost all community cultures permitted the use of supernatural means of assistance. This assistance was a form of consultation with supernatural groups like witches to enquire or atone any phenomena that suppressed the communities' physical exploration. Before the coming of colonial masters, witchcraft had been part of the culture and belief of people (362).

Witchcraft is an effective practice of good in African society and also has some content of evil like Christianity. The evil classification imposed by Western psychology on African witchcraft is not the only narrative of witchcraft because there is positive witchcraft. The systems of classification using a strange format of naming contaminate the actual essence of what is and what was classified. The imperialist incursion into Africa was a complete one having various ideological substructures as seen in the government, economics and religion of the colonialist excursion in Africa. Simona Hevesioia observes that: “Both imperialism and colonialism were driven and supported by an impressive ideological platform that sustained and fed the system” (43). These platforms were used as elements of classification and exploitation to enslave the natives in Africa as part of the imperialist ideology to completely take control of the humanity of the colonized. They did this by inferiorizing it with their own concept of a superior god in Europe, which has a cultural reflection of white and lives in a place lined with the metaphor of whiteness. The conversation between Mr. Brown and Akunna in Achebe’s *Things Fall Apart* is revealing: ‘There are no other gods,’ said Mr. Brown. ‘Chukwu is the only God and all others are false. You carved a piece of wood like that one’ (he pointed at the rafters from which Akunna’s carved Ikenga hung), ‘and you call it a god. But it is still a piece of wood’ (143). Colonialism, as symbolized by Mr. Brown, initiated its imperialist objective by first reclassifying the religious ways of the natives, ritual practices like witchcraft and ancestral worship,, thus marking witchcraft as one of the first victims of such imperialist expedition in Africa. Mr. Brown, the imperialist government agent, based on the philosophy of colonialism started a system of classification that demonized everything associated with indigenous social practice to which witchcraft belonged. Hevesioia highlights the temperament of colonialism thus: “The rightfulness associated with the expansivity of colonial powers was conveniently derived from the notions of inferiority and backwardness that were attributed to the populations of the newly acquired territories. These in fact, not only helped to justify the massive geographical extension of the empire but also created the illusion of legitimacy of the whole process” (43). Hevesioia identifies “inferiority” as a political tool of the imperialist government and the indigenous ways became victims. Hevesioia continues: “The self-imposed right to execute a civilizing mission in Third World countries, conducted in order to enlighten and humanize indigenous communities, thus logically presupposed the cultural, economic, political and even moral superiority of the colonizer” (43). African Witchcraft like the Judeo Christian religious tradition has negative and positive colourations. However the imposing presence of the foreign religion and its emphasis on the exclusive nature of its form of worship to her God made a reclassification of African ways of life, thereby breaking its institutions as a means of making a case for the imperialist Christ and a certain form of God as

representation of moral light and survival. Before the emergence of the imperialist religion and its argument of a superior deity and economic system, witchcraft in Africa generally and the Igbo traditional system in particular was a system of order that regulated man's activities within his family and his immediate environment. Todd Sanders concurs that: "African notions of witchcraft are neither archaic nor static but are highly flexible and deeply attuned to the conundrums of our contemporary world" (1). However, the perception of witchcraft from the lens of colonialism contaminates the function of witchcraft in such traditional societies like Achebe's Umuofia. Negative portrayal of witchcraft is a Western creation just as the fetishization of African belief system and its relative denigration to Western belief systems. Witchcraft in *Things Fall Apart* is practiced by those who are literate in their ways and understand the economics, politics and social workings of their people which is linked to the spirit world. As Anrize Agbanusi affirms, "... there is the experience of an immaterial invisible reality. Witchcraft is part of such reality" (116). Man needs to communicate with this immaterial reality since this invisible reality is a cultural production only perceptible within a cultural system.

THE ROLE OF WITCHCRAFT IN UMUOFIA SOCIETY

The negative representation of witchcraft in Africa and the Christian imagination did not allow so many scholars to see the importance of witchcraft which is a supernatural communing within Umuofia. This popular imagination of representing witchcraft as evil ignores other positive role of witchcraft practices in Umuofia. Matsobane J. Manaia captures this negative portrayal succinctly:

Witchcraft is probably one of the most abused, misused, and misconstrued concepts to be used to paint the whole of Africa and Africans with a broad negative brush. First and foremost, scholars and lay people define witchcraft as the belief that humans are capable of invoking, practicing and exercising psychic force for the primary source of hurting or killing other humans, and engaging in other malevolent activities (8).

This western scale of classification did not allow others to see the good in witchcraft in traditional Igbo society of Umuofia to the extent that fifty years after the publication of *Things Fall Apart*, most scholars have shied away from engaging the spirituality of Umuofia and in particular witchcraft. Witchcraft played a pivotal role of curbing security concerns in the Igbo society of Umuofia. This is reflected in Achebe's avid description of the nighttime being void of any form of social activities. M.S Jayeola-Ompyeni et al corroborate the foregoing thus:

Witchcraft in Nigeria was as old as humanity itself. It had been an issue that affected the people greatly. It was rooted in the custom and lifestyle of each of the communities. Magic, sorcery and witchcraft, had always been part of tribal issues and religion which affected almost all the Nigerian peoples at some stages of their history... (366).

Umuofia in *Things Fall Apart* is implicated in the foregoing submission because it is imagined with the literary marker of Nigeria. The night, which is governed by certain norms of Umuofia society, is clearly principle of religious practice of the people in their communing with the spirits. Irrespective of whether the intentions are ill or good, parents utilized certain strategies and linguistic expressions to educate children about their social responsibilities. Adults also mostly avoided nighttime movements as the society was dominated by the fear of the unknown. This social behavior is evident in the novel's authorial voice: "Darkness held a vague terror for these people, even the bravest among them. Children were warned not to whistle at night for the fear of evil spirits. Dangerous animals became even more sinister and uncanny in the dark. A snake was never called by its name at night, because it would hear. It was called a string" (8). The night held many fears for the people of Umuofia. Its non-illuminational properties reflected psychologically on community security and aided the checkmating of ills usually perpetrated at odd hours. Noticeably, Achebe emphasizes the fact that fear of the spirits at night helped deter even the bravest criminals and allowed for peace and quiet once the sunset and darkness subsume Umuofia. There could have also been the possibility that there might not have been the necessary need for them to have night watches as the spirits of the land had a protective shield over the people. The fear of the spirits at nighttime also gave room for the children in the community to be cultured about what they spoke at night as they lived in fear that whatever was spoken might become reality. This is in line with Christopher N Ibenwa and Tochukwu Okeke submission while commenting on tradition life; "... within the traditional life, the individual is immersed in a religious participation, which starts before birth and continues after death, for the life of an Igbo man is like a religious drama, which vitally links the living with the ancestors and those yet unborn in a mystic continuum" (2). The people of Umuofia are immersed in religious practices and some of them have the power to relate with the supernatural in their immediate community. The persons having power within the Umuofia society to relate with the supernatural did not use their power to harm the community rather they provide solutions for the challenges of the people. The foregoing is in line with Arinze Agbanusi's definition of witchcraft which is premised on the use of magic

powers... (1). Many in the Umuofia community used magical powers for collective good.

THE JUDICIAL ROLE OF WITCHCRAFT IN THE UMUOFIA SOCIETY

T.S. Petrus and D.L. Bogopa capture the functionality of witchcraft in traditional African society. They submit that "... he/she operates in both natural and supernatural realms. The witch is both a human being, with a natural, physical and, at the same time, also a "supernatural" being, able to control both material and supernatural forces for evil" (30). Okonkwo and each of the nine elders of Egwugwu change forms and in modern times can be referred to as a witch. Achebe captures the supernatural nature of the Egwugwus thus:

Each of the nine Egwugwu represents a village of the clan. Their leader was called Evil Forest. Smoke poured out of his head. The nine villages of Umuofia had grown out of the nine sons of the first father of the clan. Evil Forest represented the village of Umueru, or the children of Eru, who was the eldest of the nine sons.

'Umuofia kwenu!'

'Yaa!'

'Umuofia kwenu'

'Yaa' (71).

This is the depiction of the supernatural nature of humans who operate within the framework of spirit and human. In capturing witchcraft practice in an attempt to pass justice, Achebe accounts for the source of the spirit that possessed Okonkwo and the other Egwugwu elders; "The Egwugwu with the springy walk was one of the dead fathers of the clan (72). This illustrates that performing within Egwugwu cult requires certain transformation. Witchcraft was seen as a legal decision making sense of reason in Umuofia. It served as a voice of conscience to the people, such that they did not err in decision-making especially when it came to judicial matters. This is reflected during times of war with neighboring communities. The Oracle of the Hills and Caves portrayed justice in the land as it, through "*agadi-nwanyi* would never fight what the Igbo call *a fight of blame* (10). It is safe to say that the Oracle of Umuofia society advocated for peace in the land and would not support the people if they fought with their neighbors unjustly. Thus, when Okonkwo violates the week of peace, a week as instructed by the gods, he was punished for it (24). The gods of Umuofia such as Ani, defined an integral part of the lives of the people in terms of how they lived their

lives in peace. As much as Umuofia was feared among other clans, they avoided using this unique support as a means to override and oppress other smaller clans, knowing that the Oracle of the Hills and Caves would turn its back if that was the case (10). Another example of witchcraft playing the role of a just judge in Umuofia society is seen in the confrontation between Uzowulu and his wife Mgbafo. Uzowulu is found beating his wife, and the seven masked spirit of Egwugwu, in their just way of settling disputes, allowed for a fair hearing from both parties, including the brothers of Mgbafo who beat up Uzowulu and took away his wife and children. Rather than apportion blames to any side, they in their wisdom, strive to settle the dispute between the two families (72-75). This reflects a sense of justice and a fair hearing on the part of the witchcraft society as against the biased view that African Witchcraft shows concern to only those who have been offended. Humans like Chilue and Chika were representatives of the gods in human affairs. Achebe subtly describes the power of Chika as she mediates between man and the gods thus:

No one had ever beheld Agbala, except his priestess. But no one who had ever crawled into his awful shrine had come out without the fear of his power. His priestess stood by the sacred fire which she built in the heart of the cave and proclaimed the will of the god. The fire did not burn with a flame. The glowing logs only served to light up vaguely the dark figure of the priestess.

Sometimes a man came to consult the spirit of his dead father or relative (13).

The foregoing illustrates the changing form Chika takes when she interfaces between her god and man in her attempt to find solution for the problems of human. Most times she also had to intercede between a man and the spirit of his dead father or relative if he has offended them or is not living according to the principle on which the name of their family is built.

THE EFFECT OF WITCHCRAFT ON THE COMMERCIAL AND AGRICULTURAL LIFE PATTERN OF THE UMUOFIA PEOPLE

Achebe takes time; also, to focus on the agricultural perspective of the role witchcraft plays in the Umuofia society. Just as the gods of Umuofia protect and justly balance the society, they also ensure that the people are adequately taken care of. Ani, the earth goddess and source of all fertility, ensures that the people had farm produce in abundance. She is held in high esteem and the Feast of the New Yam Festival is celebrated in her honor with much pomp and pageantry (29). Due to the connection between the people and the gods of the land, the

people have implicit trust in the ability of the gods to bless them with bountiful harvest. Even Unoka, the protagonist's father, knew the ability of the gods in blessing the earth. This is seen when he consults Agbala "to find out why he always had a miserable harvest (13). From Unoka's visit to Agbala, one can deduce that the gods of Umuofia do not condone laziness on the part of their subjects. It is believed among the Igbo people that "when a man says yes, his chi says yes also (21). Thus, as Okonkwo puts his best foot forward by working hard, as against what his father stood for, even when things become difficult for him, the gods are quick to bless his work. The planting season is ushered in through ritualistic processes:

...the end of the carefree season between harvest and planting. In fact, he recovered from his illness only a few days before the Week of Peace began. And that was also the year Oknokwo broke the peace, and was punished as was the custom, by Ezeani, the priest of the earth goddess (23).

The goddess through human representative and certain religious observances ushers in the planting season and gives certain liberty on the Week of Peace to the extent that no one is allowed to be violent with the other. Okonkwo is punished by Ezeani for breaking the laws of the harvesting and planting seasons which aid the agricultural produce of the land. Affirming the law of the land on behalf of Ani for fruitful harvest, Ezeani approach Okonkwo:

Before it was dusk, Ezeani, who was the priest of the earth goddess, Ani, called on Okonkwo in his Obi. Okonkwo brought out Kola and placed it before the priest.

"Take away your kola nut. I shall not eat in the house of a man who has no respect for our gods and ancestors. "

Okonkwo tried to explain to him what his wife had done, but Ezeani seemed to pay no attention. He held a short staff in his hand which he brought down on the floor to emphasize his points.

'Listen to me,' he said when Okonkwo had spoken. 'You are not a stranger in Umuofia. You know as well as I do that our forefathers ordained the week of peace. That before we plant any crop in the earth we should observe a week in which a man does not say a harsh word to his neighbor. We live in peace with our fellows to honor our great goddess of the earth without whose blessing our

crops will not grow. You have committed a great evil.’ He brought down his staff heavily on the floor (24).

Humans are needed to communicate the judgment of the goddess to their fellow human. Man needed the goddess to bless the land for their crops to be successful, gifted man operates at the level of the natural and supernatural in maintaining the law for a successful planting. Even when some Western scholars see the functional role of African metaphysics, they still have zero classification of witchcraft as a medium of evil without any possibility of benefiting the society. Even after planting, the people still celebrate their god through a mediated medium which man has a functional role.

The Feast of the New Yam was approaching and Umuofia was in a festival mood. It was an occasion for giving thanks to Ani, the earth goddess and the source of all fertility. Ani played a greater part in the life of the people than any other deity. She was the ultimate judge of morality and conduct. And what was more, she was in close communion with the departed fathers of the clan whose bodies had been committed to earth. The Feast of the New Yam was held every year before the harvest began, to honor the earth goddess and the ancestral spirits of the clan (29).

Ezeani is in constant communion with various spirits of the land and she intercedes in various sacrifices to thank Ani for her blessings.

WITCHCRAFT AND THE RELIGIOUS LIFE OF THE UMUOFIA PEOPLE

In the Umuofia society, the gods are held in high regard. The religious life of the Umuofia people and the gods are intertwined, as illustrated in the text thus, “The Feast of the New Yam was approaching and Umuofia was in a festival mood. It was an occasion for giving thanks to Ani... and what was more, she was in close communion with the departed fathers of the clan whose bodies had been committed to earth” (29). The typical abode of the people of Umuofia shows categorically the place of religion in the lives of the people. With Okonkwo’s house as the descriptive yardstick;

“Okonkwo’s prosperity was visible in his household. He had a large compound enclosed by a thick wall of red earth. His own hut, or *obi*, stood immediately behind the only gate in the red walls. Each of his three wives had her own hut, which together formed a half moon behind the *obi*. The barn was built against one end of

the red walls...near the barn was a small house, the 'medicine house' or shrine where Okonkwo kept the wooden symbols of his personal god and of his ancestral spirits. He worshipped them with sacrifices of kola nut, food and palm-wine, and offered prayers to them on behalf of himself, his three wives and eight children" (12).

The Umuofia society revolved round the fact that the gods' presence was constant and stood ready to answer their prayers whenever the need arose. Okonkwo's altar to his personal god and ancestral spirits received fresh sacrifices daily with the hope that they would enrich him and protect his children. Unoka, his lazy father, also spoke of sacrificing to *Ifejioku*, the god of yams in order to harvest good farm produce. The nine masked spirits of *Egwugwu* represent not just the nine villages of the clan, but a spiritual concept of what the Umuofia society religiously adopted to come to their aid in times of distress (71). When Evil Forest, one of the masked spirits, asked the people who came to consult them over the family dispute, if they know his identity, the respondents demurred out of respect to their rank as cultural custodians as well as the spiritual implication of being in the presence of the representation of the spiritual aspect of their lives (73-75). Chielo, the priestess of *Agbala*, also evinces the prowess of the gods of the land when she tells *Ekwefi* that *Agbala* wants to see his daughter, *Ezinma*, when she fell ill. When Okonkwo attempted to question Chielo and make excuses, the priestess' admonition reflected the clear distinction between man and god: "Beware Okonkwo! ...Beware of exchanging words with *Agbala*. Does a man speak when a god speaks?"(80). This symbolizes the level of religious exultation of the gods in Umuofia society.

WITCHCRAFT AND PERSONAL DECISION MAKING OF THE UMUOFIA PEOPLE

The people of Umuofia venerated their gods as these deities shaped how they thought, acted and even spoke. *Ani*, the earth goddess and the source of all fertility, is reflected in the narrative as "the ultimate judge of morality and conduct" (pg. 29). Bernard Gecliko Nyabwani and Dickson Nkonge Kagen observe, "Good magic is accepted...used mainly by specialists such as medicine men, diviners and rainmakers. These practitioners use their knowledge or tap into this power for the benefit of the community. Examples of beneficial use of magic power include the treatment of diseases, counteracting misfortune, neutralizing or destroying evil power or witchcraft" (10). Therefore, the people of Umuofia wove their life pattern and decisions around the fact that the consequences of their actions would not go unpunished by the gods of the land. This could be seen in the actions of *Obiako*, a palm wine tapper who suddenly decides to give

up his trade just because “ the Oracle warned him that he would fall off a palm tree and kill himself” (16). The gods play the role of conscience, sometimes using another character in the narrative to warn the protagonist from taking certain steps or decisions that could affect the protagonist negatively. For example, Ogbuefi Ezeudu, the oldest man in Umuofia, warns Okonkwo about actively participating in the death of Ikemefuna thus: “that boy calls you father. Do not bear a hand in his death” (45). When Okonkwo started suffering the pangs of a guilty conscience, Obierika, knowingly, chastises him for getting directly involved in the ignominious act. “...if the Oracle said that my son should be killed, I would neither dispute it nor be the one to do it” (53). Thus, even Obierika understands the will of the gods and is seen as cautious in responding to Okonkwo’s predicament. Okonkwo, on the other hand is heady, makes hasty decisions, ignores the warning of Ogbuefi Ezeudu and is made to suffer the consequences of his actions.

THE USE OF LANGUAGE IN WITCHCRAFT IN *THINGS FALL APART*

Within the context of Umuofia society, one sees that the gods as well as the temporal construct of the society and its representation were aptly done by means of expanded language. Language in the text is a cultural imperative that accounts for the use of words and codes which may not be translated within the story but have static form in such native language as Egwugwu, Chi, Ilo, Ekwe, etc. The implication of this linguistic bent is the retention of indigenous codes that allow for a close understanding of indigenous culture within the marginal space of the colonised. The connotative power of the text’s language regarding African metaphysics imbues it with rich imagery and conveys indigenous aesthetics as evident in the song:

Eze elina, elina!
Sala
Eze ilikewa ya
Ikwaba akwa oligboli
Ebe Danda nechi eze
Ebe Uzuzu nete egwu
Sala (48)

The foregoing is the manifestation of the spiritual by means of the reenactment of the oral tradition in the song. The song is a method by which language is used to create a portal to “Chukwu, or God’s house” (48)”. Furthermore, language is used to create an atmosphere of tension and power dimension that is able to carry the spiritual forces existent within the construct of Umuofia such as “Aru oyim de de de diei!” which creates a comfortable atmosphere for the Egwugwu. So

language at this point materializes into a harbinger of the gods which is implicated in the religious narrative of witchcraft in Umuofia society.

CONCLUSION

The social lives of the people of Umuofia were defined based on spiritual concept that involves the celebration of new yam festival and the concept of the week of peace which Okonkwo desecrated by beating his wife. Witchcraft is a spiritual craft in traditional Igbo society of Umuofia in *Things Fall Apart* but the negative classification of colonialism limited its scope to the single story of evil. Witchcraft is a means of protection and interaction between man and his maker as obtainable in traditional society until the advent of exclusivist Christianity displaced it with the negative tag of 'evil'.

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